

PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF PROFESSIONAL ADAPTATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF YOUNG TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the process of adapting young teachers to professional activity, the formation of pedagogical skills, and effective methods for their development. The entry of young specialists into a new social environment, the problems they face, and the mechanisms for their elimination are analyzed on a scientific basis. The system of support for teachers, methodological assistance, and factors of professional development are also widely disclosed.

In the modern education system, the quality of pedagogical activity and the effectiveness of the educational process directly depend not only on the level of knowledge of students, but also on the personal and professional potential of the teacher. Especially for young specialists who are just starting their pedagogical activity, the process of professional formation is complex and multifaceted, including adaptation to the social environment, performing various professional roles, and applying pedagogical knowledge and skills in practice. The initial stage of a young teacher's career determines his future professional success. Therefore, the issues of effective start of pedagogical activity and development of pedagogical skills are of particular scientific and practical importance.

Entering a new environment, a young teacher performs tasks such as not only effectively organizing a lesson, but also conducting pedagogical and psychological dialogue with students, establishing cooperation with parents, and establishing professional relationships with colleagues. At the same time, a teacher must constantly analyze his activities, identify his strengths and weaknesses, strive to eliminate existing shortcomings, and improve his skills through the use of new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods. The professional skills of a teacher are formed as a result of the combination of his professional knowledge, practical skills, and personal qualities and need constant development.

The process of professional adaptation forms the readiness of a young teacher for professional activity, his ability to enter the social environment and perform new tasks. This process takes place in several stages. At the stage of acquaintance, the teacher gets acquainted with the new environment, gets acquainted with the norms of behavior, work procedures and standards within the team. At the stage of adaptation, the teacher accepts new social and professional values, but retains many of his old views. At the stage of assimilation, the teacher fully adapts to the team, feels like a part of it and begins to make independent decisions in the

process of activity. Finally, at the stage of identification, the teacher's personal goals are aligned with the goals of the organization, which helps him to effectively continue his professional activities. These stages serve to adapt the teacher to the social environment and develop his professional qualities.

The professional activity of a young teacher includes several roles at once. He acts not only as a teacher, but also as an educator, class leader, colleague and team member. Each role task requires a high level of flexibility, initiative and responsibility from the teacher. At the same time, it is important for the teacher to work on himself, acquire new knowledge and skills, and strive for personal and professional development. The teacher's creative approach, the ability to arouse the interest and activity of students, the level of use of effective methods and tools are the main indicators of his pedagogical skills.

The development of pedagogical skills is associated with many factors. First of all, it is necessary to gain experience and constantly analyze one's own activities. Reflection - a critical assessment of a teacher's own work and monitoring the results - is an important tool for improving pedagogical skills. It is also important to use innovative approaches in pedagogical activities, enrich lessons with interactive methods, and stimulate student activity. Interactive methods, including pedagogical technologies such as discussion, group work, role-playing games, cluster and brainstorming, not only ensure the active participation of students, but also develop the teacher's creative and communicative skills.

The support system is of great importance in the professional formation of a young teacher. The mentoring system, advanced training courses, trainings and involvement in scientific and practical conferences allow the teacher to gain experience, enrich his knowledge and express himself in a positive pedagogical environment. Encouraging and positive assessment of pedagogical achievements increases his motivation, increases interest in his work and contributes to his success in professional activities. At the same time, the presence of a teacher-mentor allows the young specialist to quickly adapt and express himself.

The main problems that teachers face during their work - lack of experience, psychological pressure and difficulties in managing the teaching process - can be overcome through methodological support, a mentoring system and practical training. These measures will help teachers feel confident, effectively implement their creative activities and improve their pedagogical skills. Thus, the professional development of teachers will be continuous and effective, which will improve the quality of education and student outcomes.

The professional development and improvement of pedagogical skills of a young teacher is a continuous process, which is carried out through adaptation to the social environment, the performance of various professional roles, methodological assistance and an innovative approach. A properly organized support system helps the teacher to feel free, quickly adapt and improve his pedagogical skills. Therefore, professional support and development of pedagogical skills of young teachers is one of the priority tasks of the modern education system. Undoubtedly, no pedagogical higher educational institution or college can produce a one hundred percent formed, highly qualified specialist. The process of formation of a teacher as a professional takes place precisely in an educational institution. Therefore, the administration of the educational institution, first of all, should take care of the new employee, create the necessary organizational and pedagogical conditions for the successful transition

from theory to practice. A positive socio-psychological environment, the presence of a teacher-mentor (coach), and methodological activities based on a person-centered approach help the teacher to express himself and adapt to any workplace.

Starting a teaching career, a young teacher enters a new social and professional environment, a new regime of mental and physical stress, a new sphere of relationships and cooperation. In this regard, from the first days of his work, each young specialist faces a number of interrelated tasks:

Finding optimal options for interaction with all participants in the educational process - students, colleagues, the administration of the educational institution and parents;

Skillfully applying the knowledge and practical skills acquired at the pedagogical institution, having previously assessed the level of use of innovative methods in the educational process and the appropriateness of introducing innovations; Assessing one's own abilities, the requirements of the new social environment, professional activities and, if necessary, trying to make adjustments to one's behavior.

The sequential solution of the above tasks is a prerequisite for the successful further socio-professional adaptation of a teacher starting his career. In the process of adaptation to work, a young teacher goes through the following stages:

Familiarization stage: The employee receives general information about the new situation, the criteria for evaluating various actions, and the norms of behavior in the team.

Adaptation (or formal introduction) stage: At this stage, the employee recognizes the main elements of the new value system and changes his orientation, but for the time being retains many of his old views.

Assimilation stage: The employee fully adapts to the environment and feels like a whole with the new group (identification).

Identification: The employee's personal goals are perceived as exactly the same as the goals of the labor organization.

The process of passing all these stages is quick and effective if not only the administration of the institution, but also, first of all, the young specialist himself, acts. A young teacher must master several professional roles at once in the process of professional adaptation: teacher, educator, class teacher, subordinate, colleague, member of the teachers' methodological association. In this regard, no matter what task the teacher faces, he must cope with it, demonstrating all his knowledge and skills (although they are often not yet at a high level). In this regard, we would like to highlight some tasks for assisting beginning teachers in the process of professional adaptation:

- Studying real difficulties and formulating urgent needs;

Providing information and advisory support in choosing advanced training programs and drawing up an individual educational path;

- Creating a data bank on educational services for young specialists;

- Organizing advanced training courses, participating in creative laboratories and trainings;

- Involvement in scientific and practical conferences and experimental work;

- Providing methodological literature, prospective planning materials and didactic materials;

Timely positive assessment of the teacher's work. Noticing the pedagogical achievements of a new employee, it is necessary to acknowledge this out loud. Praise encourages, gives confidence, increases interest in work and provides motivation. Thus, the professional formation of a young teacher takes place step by step and continuously. As a result, competent and high-quality management of the process of adaptation and formation of young teachers not only contributes to the professional growth of specialists, but also has a positive effect on the development of the educational institution and the results of students for whom the teacher works hard for his own success..

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